

A STUDY ON EVALUATING VARIOUS CHALLENGES FACED BY RELATIVES OF COVID AFFECTED PEOPLE IN SECOND WAVE

Krushita Desai

Research scholar

Mumbai University, Mumbai

Abstract:

The arrival of second wave of covid-19 is more harmful as compare to first way. Every individual had come out of the trauma of first wave and started living a normal life but the second wave has built a mental stress and anxiety. In second wave covid19 is spreading so fast that there is no vacancy for a bed in the hospital to treat a patient and less accessibility of oxygen and drugs and lack of treatment led to more mental stress and depression. Vaccination is playing a vital role in second wave of covid19 it led to a smaller number of covid cases and death rate.

Keywords: -covid19, first wave, second wave, mental stress

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Introduction:

The rapid change in universe due to faster growth of covid19. The first wave of covid19 was in 2020 from the month of march from China which has spread the virus called corona worldwide which has changed every individual's life. Mankind is facing many problems of poverty, unemployment, education, health issues and many more. There are large number of negative impacts on an individual. Many individuals lost their life due to this covid19. The second wave of covid 19 is more tripled than the first way. The second wave of covid19 pandemic has stuck India with an unforeseen fury. With massive strain in covid19 case there is huge increase in health care system. The admiration of how India handled the covid-19 first wave will dissipate now and will dissipate now and India will be judged for its lack of national capacity to deal with second wave. The second wave of pandemic was highlighted again in 2021 which caught India unawares. In second wave

covid patients facing the shortage of oxygen, medicines and other equipment and soon we may run short of medical staff. The state government has been finding out ways to tackle the challenges with solutions. The health department has been upgrading and ramping up the health facilities, which includes increasing the number of beds, and appointing the doctors and paramedics. Administration finds adequate oxygen and medicine supplies. There is also inadequacy of bed in the hospital for covid patient therefore administration and government has sanctioned many schools, colleges and hotels as a covid centers. The declining economic activity may force the center to re-impose a spending cap. This can jeopardize the ambitious plan of infrastructure spending to spur the economy. It as also disrupted the economic recovery after the national lockdown during the first wave in 2020 and threatens to ruin the middle class. The impact of first wave is more suffered and witnessed by middle class due to disastrous health expenditure and loss of life suffered, which is the economic backbone of Indian's growth story it broke the real estate sector, large amount of money invested by salaried class was permanently lost. The second was the lockdown induced job loss and salary cuts. Now the second wave induced disruption will deepen those losses. It has set back families for decades and will severely impact the private consumption expenditure.

After second wave there is a ripple effect on hospitality and restaurants businesses in major cities have taken a significant hit once again. Services like hostels, multiplex, pubs, bars, nightclubs etc., never fully recovered from first lockdown. After the first wave of covid there was a relaxation and rise in tourism, travel and aviation sectors face an uncertain future as again there is rise in covid cases which lead to second wave which made travel and tourism business shut down. Travel restrictions and lockdowns may push several airlines to bankruptcy. There is a major death rate and increase in covid cases in second wave as compare to the first wave. Due to rise in covid cases the number of victims affected by the coronavirus is more due to which there is shortage of beds in the hospitals and less access of oxygen and drugs for the covid affected patient. Now selling or providing oxygen and drugs to the patient is become the business it has been sold in the black market with the high cost. Families lose there loved one who are the victim of covid19 due the less access of oxygen and drugs in the market and if any case the oxygen or drugs are access for the treatment, they will available in the black market so the family can't afford it due to monetary issue and due to all this dark reason, they lost their

- Arm soreness

- Mild fever
- Tiredness
- Headaches
- Muscle or joint aches.

It has been observed that after taking covid19 vaccination there is a major change in covid19 cases number of cases are declining but also it has been observed that even after having the vaccination people become the victim of coronavirus and in some extreme case people are losing their life too. Somehow every mankind had faced all the challenges of covid19 in first wave and started to live a normal life but again the second wave made the life more challenging for every mankind in the universe.

Review of Literature

Moghnieh, Abdallah, Bizri: -

From 2019 to 2020 there was the first wave of coronavirus which was very infectious to every mankind across the globe and after the occurrence of second wave countries started to register a greater number of death rates and covid19 victims as compared to the first wave of covid even after taking major medical and health preventive measures. The threat of a weak immunity system in individuals there is a need to boost immunity level to fight against coronavirus. There are many individuals who are still getting infectious after taking the vaccination. For the upcoming covid19 situation all the individuals, physicians, public health agencies should be very well prepared for the more ridiculous situation on the globe. Hospitals should look forward to enhance and upgrade their medical and health care system for the upcoming scenario.

Babicki, Szewczykowska, Mastalerz-Migas:

The second wave of covid19 has doubled the stress of mankind it is affecting the mental health. The rapid change over the period and uncertainty of the next day, and the fear of death. The second wave has made an individual mentally so weak and depressed. Even the normal person who is fit and fine are dealing with mental stress and have to consult the psychological experts. The restrictions on new opportunities during the era of covid19 bring anxiety and stress which led to mental health issues. The scenario is so depressing of covid19 second wave that special programs should be conducted for mental stress management to stay positive in a negative situation for a psychological support.

Schleicher (2020): -

The second wave has forced mankind to change the cultural perspective and

educational system. The school culture has profound impact on the degree on educational innovation. Education system doesn't matter much the change of school culture attempting to school class and now the culture of online class influences the educational environment. Educational culture includes understanding the attitudes, value, and capabilities of general administration that comprise the school culture. There should be a continuous development for effective education system for a student even in covid19 pandemic. The process of change is difficult but need to be facilitated for cultural perspective for education implementation. The second wave has the risk and fear of education reform and repeating the past mistakes. The second wave has brought the fear of frustration, stress and anxiety among educational culture. It affects teacher's preparedness to support digital learning, vocational education during the covid19 lockdown is another issue for school faculty. The pandemic is also call as renew the commitment to the sustainable development goals.

Singh, Singh, Singh Sawhney (2020): -

Due to coronavirus the covid19 has affected globally. The number of death rate is very high and cases are emerging every day. The covid19 is witnessing a second wave and are threatening of many upcoming waves. Due to infectious and highly spreading virus survival of mankind has become very difficult, covid19 has created a harmful and stressful environment over the whole universe. The anxiety and stress among the people have increased so high that people think to attempt suicide. In the mind of people they have psychological fear of lack of treatment and unavailability of oxygen and drugs. Social media has become more vital and online platform has become a part of our life across the globe. The second wave has created more negative impact and emotions of stress, fear, anger and sadness.

Malhotra (2021): -

After suffering from first wave of covid19 it was just few months again there is a comeback of second wave. After first wave of covid there was a reopening of tourism industry. There was again a growth in tourism organization. The global hospitality has just started to come on the track and there was a new arrival of second wave of covid19. There was a tremendous decrease in tourism and large number of flights are getting cancelled. Again, there was a restriction to go for other states and country due to mini lockdown and enrollments of new covid cases and large number of deaths. A criterion shift in global hospitality industry is envisaged in the near future.

Objectives:

To explore various problem faced by relatives in covid19 people in second wave.

Conclusion:

In covid19 pandemic it has been observed that the second wave of coronavirus is more disastrous compare to first wave a greater number of individuals has becoming the victim of coronavirus in second wave and majority of individual is losing their life. The life has becomeso insignificant that there is a fear of tomorrow. It has been observed that there is a less accessibility of bed in hospitals for covid19 patient so in some case the patient is treated fromtheir home. The administration has made the extra arrangements for beds and other medical facilities. Even after extra facilities there is a less availability of oxygen and drugs for covid19patients. Oxygen and drugs now became a business in the market as they are available in the black market with unaffordable cost. People just started living their regular routine after the first wave of covid19 but the occurrence of second wave again demotivated the individual which led them with mental stress and depression.

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